

Piezoelectricity: History and New Thrusts

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Abstract—Piezoelectricity was discovered by the brothers Curie in 1880. What started out as a scientific curiosity has grown to have very significant commercial importance. We sketch here some of the milestones of its history, a bit of its phenomenology, and conclude with some present applications and prospects for the future.

INTRODUCTION

The term "piezoelectricity" refers to the production of bound electrical charges on surfaces of a suitable specimen by the imposition of mechanical stress. One says that the elastic and electric variables are coupled; we shall also find that the effect provides connections between a number of well-known personages, and between some seemingly disparate facts, in a most interesting manner. A good portion of the history is gleaned from Cady's book [1], which can still be read with great profit by those interested in the subject of piezoelectricity. Some of the phenomenology is taken from Ref. [2]. Let us begin with the events outlined in Table 1.

TABLE I
SCHEMATIC HISTORY OF PIEZOELECTRICITY.

• Coulomb	conjecture
• Haüy	experiments
• Becquerel	experiments, 1820
• Curie, P. & J.	discovery, 1880
• Hankel	"piezoelectricity," 1881
• Lippmann	converse effect, 1881; found by Curies, 1881; same coefficient
• Kelvin,	atomic model, 1893;
• Duhem,	phenomenological
• Pockels	theory
• Voigt	1894, "tensor," Lehrbuch, 1910
• Langevin	sonar, c. 1914-1918; ultrasonics
• Born	theo. calc. e of β -ZnS, 1920

Coulomb [3] is said to have conjectured that electricity might be produced by pressure; this led to experiments by Haüy [4] and A C Becquerel [5] with inconclusive results; any charges produced might have been caused by friction or contact electricity. Becquerel did make a prescient remark in respect to charges occasioned by stretching rubber; he conjectured that experiments with crystalline minerals might show effects due to their anisotropy [8].

The undoubted discoverers of the phenomenon of piezoelectricity were the Curie brothers. They knew what they were looking for, and had the backgrounds and facilities to bring the search to a successful conclusion [9]. Their pictures appear as the frontispiece in Cady, and in Ref. [10]. They announced their discovery as follows:

"Those crystals having one or more axes whose ends are unlike, that is to say hemihedral crystals with oblique faces, have the special physical property of giving rise to two electrical poles of opposite signs at the extremities of these axes when they are subjected to a change in temperature: this is the phenomenon known under the name of *pyroelectricity*."

"We have found a new method for the development of polar electricity in these same crystals, consisting in subjecting them to variations in pressure along their hemihedral axes."

P. & J. Curie

"Development by pressure of polar electricity in hemihedral crystals with inclined faces," Bull. soc. min. de France, vol. 3, pp. 90-93, 1880. Read on April 8, 1880. Quoted in Cady, *Piezoelectricity*, 1946.

In 1881, Hankel [11] suggested the name "piezoelectricity," which was accepted by all. Also in 1881, Lippmann [12], on thermodynamic grounds, asserted that the converse effect should exist as well, that is, imposition of surface charge induces mechanical deformation. The Curies verified this in the same year, and showed that the coefficients for both the direct and converse effects were identical.

Lord Kelvin [13] developed an atomic model to describe the effect in 1893 [14]; this is explained and expanded in Ref. [15]. The phenomenology of piezoelectricity was advanced substantially by Duhem [16] and Pockels [17], but with the work of Woldemar Voigt [18-20] it can be said to have reached maturity.

CRYSTAL SYSTEM	CENTRIC POINT GROUPS		ACENTRIC POINT GROUPS					OPTIC AXES
			POLAR		NONPOLAR			
TRICLINIC	$\bar{1}$		1		NONE			B I A X I A L
MONOCLINIC	2/m		2	m	NONE			
ORTHORHOMBIC	mmm		mm2		222			
TETRAGONAL	4/m	4/mmm	4	4mm	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{4}2m$	422	U N I A X I A L
TRIGONAL	$\bar{3}$	$\bar{3}m$	3	3m	32			
HEXAGONAL	6/m	6/mmm	6	6mm	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{6}m2$	622	
CUBIC	m3	m3m	NONE		23	$\bar{4}3m$	432	ISOTROPIC
	11 GROUPS		10 GROUPS		11 GROUPS			

Figure 1. The crystallographic point groups

Figure 2. Heckmann diagram

During the period 1914-1918, Langevin [22] applied piezoelectric transducers to the problem of submarine detection; he thus became the father of sonar and of the discipline of ultrasonics. Born [24], in 1920, published the first lattice-theoretical calculation of a piezoelectric coefficient, that of β -ZnS.

The piezoelectric effect remained largely a curiosity until 1921 when Cady [25] utilized its presence in quartz to realize crystal resonators for the stabilization of oscillators. See also [26]. Bechmann [27], one of the four independent discoverers of the zero-temperature-coefficient AT and BT cuts of quartz in the period 1933-34, contributed greatly to the field of frequency control. Another estimable contributor to many areas of applied piezoelectricity was Mason [28]. In Ref. [15] he explained and extended the Kelvin model; he invented the quartz GT cut in 1940, and is responsible for the equivalent circuit model that bears his name.

POINT GROUPS AND CURIE SAMPLES

Piezoelectricity is found in many substances, such as bone, wood, and ice. Because of its polar nature, it depends on an asymmetry in the structure of the material. Most piezoelectrics are crystals, and it is found that the effect depends upon the crystallographic symmetry, in particular, that of the point groups. Figure 1 shows the thirty-two point groups [31]; the twenty piezoelectric groups are those under the heading 'acentric,' with the exception of class 432. The point group also establishes the forms of the elastic, piezoelectric, and dielectric matrices. Additional details are given in Refs. [32-39]. In Table 2 are listed the samples reported by the Curies in 1880 along with the point group. Topaz is usually accorded symmetry *mmm*. One sees the well-placed representation of groups in their sample.

TABLE 2
CRYSTALS MEASURED BY THE CURIE BROTHERS FOR THE PRESENCE OF PIEZOELECTRICITY.

Crystal	Formula	Class
zincblende/sphalerite	β -ZnS	4 3 m
sodium chlorate	Na Cl O ₃	2 3
boracite	Mg ₃ B ₇ O ₁₃ Cl	4 3 m
tourmaline	Na Mg ₃ B ₃ Al ₆ Si ₆ O ₂₇ • (OH) ₄	3 m
quartz	Si O ₂	3 2
calamine/hemimorphite	Zn ₄ (OH) ₂ Si ₂ O ₇ • H ₂ O	mm2
topaz	Al ₂ Si O ₄ (F, OH) ₂	mm2 ?
tartaric acid	H ₂ C ₄ • H ₄ O ₆	2
cane sugar/sucrose	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₁	2
Rochelle Salt/sodium potassium tartarate	K Na (C ₄ H ₄ O ₆) • 4 H ₂ O	2 2 2

In 1925, G Heckmann of Göttingen published a very instructive schematic representation of couplings between elastic, electric, and thermal variables [40]; these have been modified and embellished by others ever since [41]. A version of the Heckmann diagram is shown in Fig. 2.

CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS

The phenomenological equations that govern the linear macroscopic behavior of piezoelectrics are listed in matrix form in Table 3; a prime denotes transpose. The third set ($S = s^E T + d' E$) says that stress (T) is proportional to strain (S); Ref. [44], and also is proportional to electric field; this represents the converse effect; the piezo portion of its companion ($D = d T + \epsilon^T E$), represents the direct effect. One sees that the piezoelectric coefficient that couples the mechanical and electrical variables is the same in both equations, as the Curies found.

TABLE 3
ELASTO-PIEZO-DIELECTRIC CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS

$$\begin{array}{ll} T = c^E S - e' E & D = e S + \epsilon^S E \\ T = c^D S - h' D & E = -h S + \beta^S D \\ S = s^E T + d' E & D = d T + \epsilon^T E \\ S = s^D T + g' D & E = -g T + \beta^T D \end{array}$$

The first set written out in tensor notation is:

- $T_{\lambda} = c_{\lambda\mu}^E S_{\mu} - e_{m\lambda} E_m$
- $D_m = e_{m\lambda} S_{\lambda} + \epsilon_{mj}^S E_j$

It was Voigt who first converted the second-rank, three-dimensional stress and strain tensors into first-rank, six-dimensional tensors so that the constitutive equations given above could be represented in two-dimensional form. Matrices are simpler than three-dimensional stacks!

The choice of independent variables determines the particular piezoelectric constant, as is seen in Table 3. The names and units of the most often used piezoelectric constants are given in Table 4. The 'a' and 'b' constants are used when polarization is used as a variable in place of electric field, E, or electric displacement, D. The polarization coefficients are used primarily for electro-optical applications.

$$W_1 = (1/2)(1/c^E)T_1^2$$

$$W_2 = W_1[k^2/(1+k^2)]$$

$$D_2 = D_1 = (e/c^E)T_1$$

Figure 3. Piezoelectric cycle

Point Group	$c_{m\lambda}$	c_{11}	c_{12}	c_{13}	c_{14}	c_{15}	c_{16}	c_{21}	c_{22}	c_{23}	c_{24}	c_{25}	c_{26}	c_{31}	c_{32}	c_{33}	c_{34}	c_{34}	c_{34}
1		11	12	13	14	15	16	21	22	23	24	25	26	31	32	33	34	35	36
2		0	0	0	14	0	16	21	22	23	0	25	0	0	0	0	34	0	36
m		11	12	13	0	15	0	0	0	0	24	0	26	31	32	33	0	35	0
4, 6		0	0	0	14	15	0	0	0	0	15	-14	0	31	31	33	0	0	0
422, 622		0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	-14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4mm, 6mm		0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	31	31	33	0	0	0
3		11	-11	0	14	15	-22	-22	22	0	15	-14	-11	31	31	33	0	0	0
32		11	-11	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	-14	-11	0	0	0	0	0	0
3m		0	0	0	0	15	-22	-22	22	0	15	0	0	31	31	33	0	0	0
mm2		0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	24	0	0	31	32	33	0	0	0
$\bar{4}$		0	0	0	14	15	0	0	0	0	-15	14	0	31	-31	0	0	0	36
$\bar{6}$		11	-11	0	0	0	-22	-22	22	0	0	0	-11	0	0	0	0	0	0
$\bar{6}m2$		11	-11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-11	0	0	0	0	0	0
222		0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	26	0	0	0	0	0	0	36
$\bar{4}2m$		0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	36
23, $\bar{4}3m$		0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	14

Figure 4. Piezoelectric matrices for all twenty classes

TABLE 4.
PIEZOELECTRIC COEFFICIENTS

Stress Constant	e	C/m ²
Strain Coefficient	d	m/V = C/N
Stress Modulus	h	N/C = V/m
Strain Constant	g	m ² /C
Polarization Modulus	a	N/C = V/m
Polarization Constant	b	m ² /C

The different elastic, piezoelectric, and dielectric coefficients are interrelated; the relations are given in Table 5. For point group 6mm, which includes poled ceramics [45], the difference relations are written out explicitly from the matrices given in, e.g., Refs. [1, 20, 30, 34, 43], as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{11}^D - c_{11}^E &= e_{31}^2 / \epsilon_{33}^S; & c_{12}^D - c_{12}^E &= e_{31}^2 / \epsilon_{33}^S \\ c_{13}^D - c_{13}^E &= e_{33}^2 / \epsilon_{33}^S; & c_{44}^D - c_{44}^E &= e_{15}^2 / \epsilon_{11}^S \\ c_{66}^D - c_{66}^E &= 0; & \epsilon_{11}^T - \epsilon_{11}^S &= e_{15}^2 s_{44}^E \\ \epsilon_{33}^T - \epsilon_{33}^S &= 2e_{31}^2 (s_{11}^E + s_{12}^E) + 4e_{31}e_{33}s_{13}^E + e_{33}^2 s_{33}^E \end{aligned}$$

TABLE 5.
INTERRELATIONSHIPS

$$c^X s^X \equiv e^Y \beta^Y \equiv I; \text{ X is E or D and Y is T or S}$$

$$\begin{aligned} e &= \epsilon^S h = d c^E & d &= \epsilon^T g = e s^E \\ h &= \beta^S e = g c^D & g &= \beta^T d = h s^D \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} c^D - c^E &= h' e = e' h = h' \epsilon^S h = e' \beta^S e \\ s^E - s^D &= g' d = d' g = g' \epsilon^T g = d' \beta^T d \\ \epsilon^T - \epsilon^S &= e d' = d e' = e s^E e' = d c^E d' \\ \beta^S - \beta^T &= g h' = h g' = h s^D h' = g c^D g \end{aligned}$$

One might well ask 'Why constitutive equations?' The answer is simply '10²³!' The relatively few material constants in the equations of Table 3 stand in for the enormous interactions between atoms. The simplification is astounding, but it is not simple!

We are told that there are but four basic interactions (forces) in nature: 1) weak interactions between leptons, baryons, and mesons; these are responsible, e.g., for neutron decay/radioactivity (H Becquerel again!); but these are of very short range, < few fm. 2) strong interactions between hadrons (baryons and mesons); again of very short range, < few fm. 3) gravitational interactions [3]; long range, inverse-square, but very, very weak compared to: 4) electromagnetic interactions which are of long range and effect primarily charged particles. The electrical and mechanical (elastic) forces in the constitutive equations are electromagnetic. Yet Coulomb's force law [3], is inverse-square between particles. Why are both Hooke's (elastic) law and the piezoelectric equation linear? The answer here is deep. It is the

massive cancellations that take place among the '10²³' particles that renders the equations (to a first approximation) linear. By sheer coincidence, the bound motion of two classical particles mutually subject to a central force law possesses closed (elliptical) orbits only for the exceptional cases of Hookean (linear) and Coulombic (inverse-square) attraction.

COUPLING COEFFICIENTS

More important by far than the piezoelectric coefficients are the dimensionless combinations of material parameters called piezocoupling coefficients. These are listed in Table 6, and arise from the particular forms of the constitutive equations used. Table 7 gives some of their applications.

TABLE 6.
PIEZOELECTRIC COUPLING COEFFICIENTS, k

$$\begin{aligned} k_{\text{hom}}^2 &= d^2 / (\epsilon^T s^E) = h^2 / (\beta^S c^D) \\ &= e^2 / (\epsilon^T c^E) = e^2 / (\epsilon^S c^D) = g^2 / (\beta^T s^E) = g^2 / (\beta^S s^D) \\ k_{\text{mix}}^2 &= e^2 / (\epsilon^S c^E) = g^2 / (\beta^T s^D) \\ &= d^2 / (\epsilon^S s^E) = d^2 / (\epsilon^T s^D) = h^2 / (\beta^S c^E) = h^2 / (\beta^T c^D) \end{aligned}$$

TABLE 7.
WHY COUPLING COEFFICIENTS?

COMPONENT/DEVICE	PARAMETER
Transducers; Filters	Bandwidth; Insertion loss
Resonators; Resonant MEMS	Pole-Zero spacing
Actuators; Sensors	Elec-mech conversion η

PIEZOELECTRIC CYCLES

One may see the importance of coupling factors in yet another way. By constructing the piezo equivalent of a thermodynamic cycle, the interchange of energies may be traced. A simple cycle is shown in Fig. 3, wherein it is seen that the intermediate values are functions of k.

NEUMANN'S PRINCIPLE

Franz Neumann [21] established a fundamental principle governing the physical behavior of crystalline materials [1, 36, 37, 43]. It may be stated in several equivalent forms:

MATERIAL/CUT	CLASS	COUPLING FACTOR
Lithium niobate crystal X-cut 36° rotated-Y-cut	3m	$k_{15} = 68.9\%$ $k_{22} = 48.7\%$
Quartz crystal AT-cut BT-cut	32	$k'_{26} = 8.8\%$ $k'_{26} = 5.0\%$
PZT ceramic solid solutions Z-cut	∞ mm	$k_{33} = 30$ to 60%
Polyvinylidene fluoride, PVDF Z-normal sheet	mm2	$k_{31} = 16\%$
Gallium Arsenide (110)-cut (111)-cut	$\bar{4}3m$	$k'_{26} = 6.1\%$ $k'_{11} = 4.3\%$
Silicon Carbide, α -SiC X- or Y-cut Z-cut	6mm	$k_{15} = 2.5\%$ $k_{33} = 3.5\%$
Zinc Oxide Z-normal, thin film	6mm	$k_{15} = 26\%$ $k_{33} = 29\%$
Aluminum Nitride Z-normal, thin film	6mm	$k_{15} = 15.5\%$ $k_{33} = 24.2\%$

Figure 5. Coupling factors of representative materials

- The symmetry elements of any physical property of a crystal must include all the symmetry elements of the point group of the crystal.

- Every physical property of a crystal must possess at least the symmetry of the point group of the crystal.

- Any kind of symmetry that is possessed by the crystallographic form of a material is possessed by the material in respect of every physical property.

INDEPENDENT CONSTANTS

The crystallographic point groups determine the forms of the elastic, piezoelectric, and dielectric matrices (and those of other effects represented in phenomenological form). The number of independent constants for the piezoelectric groups are given in Table 8. Figure 4 gives the explicit forms for the piezoelectric 'e' matrices for all classes.

TABLE 8
NUMBER OF INDEPENDENT CONSTANTS FOR POLAR GROUPS

CLASS	1	2	m	mm2	4
$c_{\lambda\mu}$	21	13	13	9	7
$e_{m\lambda}$	18	8	10	5	4
ϵ_{mn}	6	4	4	3	2
TOTAL	45	25	27	17	13

POLAR GROUPS (CONTINUED)

CLASS	4mm	3	3m	6	6mm
$c_{\lambda\mu}$	6	7	6	5	5
$e_{m\lambda}$	3	6	4	4	3
ϵ_{mn}	2	2	2	2	2
TOTAL	11	15	12	11	10

TABLE 8
NUMBER OF INDEPENDENT CONSTANTS FOR NONPOLAR GROUPS

CLASS	222	4	42m	422	32
$c_{\lambda\mu}$	9	7	6	6	6
$e_{m\lambda}$	3	4	2	1	2
ϵ_{mn}	3	2	2	2	2
TOTAL	15	13	10	9	10

NONPOLAR GROUPS (CONTINUED)

CLASS	6	6m2	622	23	43m
$c_{\lambda\mu}$	5	5	5	3	3
$e_{m\lambda}$	2	1	1	1	1
ϵ_{mn}	2	2	2	1	1
TOTAL	9	8	8	5	5

REPRESENTATIVE VALUES

Figure 5 gives values for the piezocoupling factors of representative materials. Of particular note are the semiconductors GaAs and α -SiC for future applications. Almost all of the binary semiconductors are piezoelectric, belonging either to the 6mm or 43m groups. These are well suited for uses where

both the piezoelectric and semiconducting properties are required.

PIEZOELECTRIC FORCES

The volumetric force densities due to the piezoelectric effect are given by the stress gradients as follows:

- $F_j = \partial T_{ij} / \partial X_i$ (newton / m³)
- $T_{ij} = c^E_{ijkl} S_{kl} - e_{mij} E_m$
- F_j (piezo) = $-\partial (e_{mij} E_m) / \partial X_i$

APPLICATIONS

Devices based on piezoelectricity have expanded dramatically in application beyond the crystal oscillator. Piezoelectric devices are additionally used as transducers in applications from telephone speakers to sonar arrays; a newer and rapidly burgeoning area of utilization is the integral incorporation of mechanical actuation and sensing microstructures into electronic chips. These microelectromechanical structures (MEMS) promise signal sensing, processing, and outputting features unattainable by exclusively electronic/photonic means.

One of the most appealing aspects of piezoelectricity for modern applications is the compelling immediacy and simplicity of the transduction mechanism. Micro- and nano-electronics are built upon the behavior of charged species subjected to electric fields; the extreme miniaturization of these structures is owed in large measure to their ability to take on a capacitor-like form. Bulky inductors are banished and thin, planar electrodes introduce the electric fields to operate the circuits. These fields also provide the forces required to drive mechanical motions in a piezoelectric device. Elastic field/mechanical considerations can, therefore, be incorporated into the operations of modern electronic components in a clean, efficient, and very direct manner, by making use of the voltages resident on the chips, via the piezoeffect.

Some of the areas of application of modern piezoelectric devices are listed in schematic fashion in Table 9. The list is meant to be representative, rather than inclusive.

TABLE 9.
SOME PIEZOELECTRIC APPLICATIONS

COMMUNICATIONS & CONTROL

- cellular radio • TV • automotive radar
- o signal processing & frequency control
 - correlators; convolvers
 - filters; delay lines
 - oscillators, etc.

HEALTH & CONSUMER

- transducers • sensors • actuators
 - pumps • motors

- o noninvasive medical diagnostics
- o hyperthermia o lithotripsy
- o subcutaneous medication

- o wristwatches
- o camera focusing/steadying/ranging
- o computer timing/printing/modems
- o ignition of gases ("spark pump")
- o phonograph pickup (passé !)

INDUSTRIAL

- transducers • sensors • actuators
 - pumps • motors

- o ultrasonic cleaning o sonar
- o nondestructive evaluation (NDE)
- o liquid level sensors
- o vibration damping
- o high temperature sensors
- o high voltage generators/transformers
- o material properties determination
- o chem/bio-sensors

NEWER APPLICATIONS

- smart structures
 - o microelectromechanical (MEMS) devices
 - o microoptomechanical (MOMS) devices
 - o biomimetic devices

- high displacement transducers
 - o composite & functionally graded devices
 - o smarties o moonies o rainbows

- mixed-effect devices
 - o acousto-phonic-electronic devices

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REFERENCES AND NOTES

[1] W G Cady, *Piezoelectricity*, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1946; Dover, New York, 1964.

[2] A Ballato, "Piezoelectricity: Old Effect, New Thrusts," IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelec., Freq. Contr., Vol. 42, No. 5, September 1995, pp. 916-926.

[3] Charles Augustin de Coulomb (1736-1806), was inventor of the torsion balance (c. 1784), with which he established the force law for electric charges that bears his name. A torsion balance was also used to verify the law of gravity, the only other fundamental force law that is inverse-square. This was done in 1798, by Henry Cavendish (1731-1810), using the independent invention of the Rev. John Michell.

[4] Abbé René Just Haüy (1743-1822), mineralogist; is called "the father of crystallography."

[5] Antoine César Becquerel (1788-1878); his son, Edmond Becquerel (1820-1891) was the father of Antoine Henri Becquerel (1852-1908), who discovered radioactivity and who received a Nobel prize in physics in 1903, 'in recognition of the extraordinary services he has rendered by his discovery of spontaneous radioactivity.' The Curies [6, 7] shared half the prize.

[6] Pierre Curie (1859-1906) and Marie Curie (1867-1934), née Marya Sklodowska; Nobel prize in physics, 1903, 'in recognition of the extraordinary services they have rendered by their joint researches on the radiation phenomena discovered by Professor Henri Becquerel.'

[7] Marie Curie, née Marya Sklodowska (1867-1934); Nobel prize in chemistry in 1911, 'in recognition of her services to the advancement of chemistry by the discovery of the elements radium and polonium, by the isolation of radium and the study of the nature and compounds of this remarkable element.'

[8] A C Becquerel, in Bull. soc. philomath. Paris, ser. 3, Vol.7, 1820, pp. 149-155. The statement under discussion appears in [1], p. 177.

[9] Pierre Curie (1859-1906). Research on symmetry, sensitive measurement instruments, temperature effects on magnetism, and radioactivity; see also Ref. [6]. Jacques (Paul-Jacques) Curie (1855-1941). Researches in the area of mineralogy, particularly pyroelectricity and piezoelectricity.

[10] Ferroelectrics, Vol. 40, Nos. 3/4, 1982; Vol. 41, Nos. 1/2/3/4, 1982; Vol. 42, Nos. 1/2/3/4, 1982; Vol. 43, Nos. 1/2, 1982 Special Issue on Piezoelectricity, Parts I-IV; pictures of the Curie brothers appear on page iii of each Part.

[11] Wilhelm Gottlieb Hankel (1814-1899), of Halle and Leipzig; worked in areas of physics and electricity. Hermann Hankel (1839-1873), noted for his function-theoretic investigations of Bessel and related functions, was his son.

[12] Gabriel Lippmann (1845-1921); Nobel prize in physics, 1908, 'for his method of reproducing colours photographically based on the phenomenon of interference.'

[13] William Thomson, Lord Kelvin (1824-1907). Physicist and engineer; devised the absolute temperature scale, advanced the theory of heat, designs of submarine cables and mariner's compass, etc.

[14] W Thomson (Lord Kelvin), *Baltimore Lectures on Molecular Dynamics and the Wave Theory of Light*, Cambridge University Press, London, 1904. Lectures delivered October 1884; Appendix E, November 1901, pp. 562 ff.

[15] W P Mason, *Quartz Crystal Applications*, Chapter 1, pp.11-56, in R A Heising, *Quartz Crystals for Electrical Circuits*, Van Nostrand, New York, 1946.

[16] Pierre-Maurice-Marie Duhem (1861-1916); noted thermodynamicist.

[17] Frederick Pockels (1865-1913); established, in 1893, the linear electro-optic effect that bears his name.

- [18] Woldemar Voigt (1850-1919) of Königsberg and Göttingen; studied under Franz Neumann [21]. Made monumental contributions in the areas of crystal physics, elasticity, thermodynamics, magneto-optics, and electro-optics [19, 20]. Along with Gregorio Ricci-Curbastro (1853-1925) and Tullio Levi-Civita (1873-1941) established "tensor analysis."
- [19] W Voigt, Die fundamentalen physikalischen Eigenschaften der Kristalle, Teubner, Leipzig, 1898.
- [20] W Voigt, Lehrbuch der Kristallphysik, Teubner, Leipzig, 1910; 2nd impression, 1928.
- [21] Franz Ernst Neumann (1798-1895); revered professor at the University of Königsberg. Taught crystallography and theoretical physics; worked in the areas of optics, mathematical physics (Bessel function of the second kind, etc.), elastic theory of light, physics of crystals, magnetism, and induction; see, e.g., [21a]. His activities and those of others, such as Friedrich Wilhelm Bessel (1784-1846), led to a flowering of mathematical physics at Königsberg, producing many illustrious students such as Gustav Robert Kirchhoff (1824-1887) and Arnold Sommerfeld (1868-1951). Sommerfeld, in turn, was mentor to many Nobel laureates.
- [21a] F Neumann, Vorlesungen über die Theorie der Elasticität, Leipzig, 1885.
- [21b] Carl Gottfried Neumann (1832-1925); professor of mathematics at Leipzig was the son of F E Neumann.
- [22] Paul Langevin (1872-1946), physicist, educator, and author, was noted for his work on the atomic theory of paramagnetism. André (b. 1901), one of his four children, also published in the area of piezoelectricity. Paul's protégé, F. Joliot, married Irène Curie [23]. Their daughter Héléne married Paul's grandson. See also [15].
- [23] Frédéric Joliot (1900-1958) and Irène Joliot-Curie (1897-1956); Nobel prize in chemistry in 1935, 'in recognition of their synthesis of new radioactive elements.'
- [24] Max Born (1882-1970); Nobel prize in physics, 1954, 'for his fundamental research in quantum mechanics, especially for his statistical interpretation of the wavefunction.'
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